

EXPERIMENTAL

2,4-Dimethylphenol was distilled before use, b.p. 211° . β -Propiolactone was supplied by Eastman Kodak Co. Thiophenol and *p*-ethoxythiophenol required for the work were prepared according to the method of Tarbell and Fukushima⁴.

Substituted β -phenoxypropionic acids were prepared from 4-chloro-3,5-dimethylphenol, 2,4-dimethylphenol, and 2,4-dibromophenol in the following way. β -Propiolactone (0.1M) was added gradually to phenol or thiophenol (0.1M), dissolved in a solution of $NaOH$ (0.1M) in water (40 ml) and isolated in the usual way according to Gresham *et al.*⁵

The m.p.s, yields, neutralisation equivalents, and analyses of the phenoxypropionic acids are recorded in Table I.

β -(Thiophenoxy)propionic acid, m.p. $57-58^\circ$, was obtained in 80% yield, as reported by Gresham *et al.*⁵

4. "Organic Syntheses", Col. Vol. III, p. 809.

5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 681.

TABLE I

Substituted β -phen- Oxypropionic acids.	M.P.	Yield	Nont. equiv.		%Carbon		%Hydrogen	
			Found.	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
4-Chloro- 3,5-dimethyl	90°	43%	227.9	228.9	57.3	57.7	5.40	5.69
2,4-Dimethyl	118°	30	193.4	194.0	67.6	68.0	7.10	7.22
2,4-Dibromo	109°	60	323.0	324.0	33.0	33.3	2.25	2.47

β -(*p*-Ethoxythiophenoxy)propionic acid, m.p. 68°, was obtained in 90% yield (Found: S, 14.4%; $C_{11}H_{14}O_3S$ requires S, 14.16%).

Chromanones and Thiochromanones

β -Phenoxypropionic acids (IIIa) and β -thiophenoxypropionic acids (IIIb) were cyclised to chromanones (IVa) and thiochromanones (IVb) either by 98% H_2SO_4 (cono.) method⁶ (A) or by P_2O_5 in dry benzene, method⁷ (B).

The chromanones and thiochromanones, thus obtained, were characterised through their 2,4-DNPs. The m.p.s yields, m.p.s. of 2,4-DNPs and their analyses are reported in Table II.

TABLE II

	M.P. or B.P.	Yield	Method.	% Carbon		% Hydrogen		M.P.	2,4 DNP.	
				Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.		Found.	Reqd.
I. Chromanone.										
6-Chloro- 5,7-dimethyl	68°	95%	A	62.2	62.7	5.00	5.23	262°	14.10	14.34
6,8-Dimethyl	152°/6mm	90	B	74.8	75.0	6.39	6.82	265°	15.41	15.73
6,8-Dibromo-	165°/6	90	B	35.8	35.3	1.80	1.96	>270°	11.20	11.52
II. Thiochromanone.										
6-Ethoxy-	154°/12	90	B	69.1	69.5	5.45	5.77	265°	14.06	14.43
Thiochromanone	158°/10	70	A	Hard and Hayne ⁶ reported b.p. 154°/12mm, yield 71%						

The Mannich base hydrochlorides from substituted chromanones were obtained as described below.

A mixture of the chromanone (0.01*M*), paraformaldehyde (0.01*M*), and dry benzene was refluxed on a water bath for 30 min. Amine hydrochloride (0.01*M*) was then added to the reaction mixture which was refluxed again for about 10 min. It was then acidified either with 5 or 10 drops of HCl (cono.) or by passing dry HCl gas; the reaction mixture was refluxed again for 6 to 8 hr. during which the Mannich base hydrochloride separated as a fine crystalline mass. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the crystalline mass was filtered, washed with dry benzene, and finally recrystallised from anhydrous ethanol. The m.p.s., yields, and analysis of the Mannich base hydrochlorides are recorded in Table III.

6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 5065

7. Robertson and Subramaniam, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 183.

TABLE III

	R' & R''.	M.P.	Yield	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
R ₁ = R ₂ = 6-chloro-5, 7-dimethyl.						
1	Morpholino	162°	55 %	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₃ NCI ₂	3.90	4.06
2	Piperidine	225°	50	C ₁₇ H ₂₃ O ₃ NCI ₂	3.81	4.07
3	Di-n-propylamino	265°	35	C ₁₈ H ₂₇ O ₃ NCI ₂	3.64	3.89
4	Di-isobutylamino	> 265°	40	C ₂₀ H ₃₁ O ₃ NCI ₂	3.28	3.61
5	Dibutylamino	> 265°	50	C ₂₀ H ₃₁ O ₃ NCI ₂	3.35	3.61
R ₁ = R ₂ = 6, 8-dimethyl.						
6	Morpholino	165°	50	C ₁₅ H ₂₁ O ₃ NCI	4.20	4.67
7	Piperidino	230°	45	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₃ NCI	4.50	4.71
8	Dimethylamino	125°	30	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ O ₃ NCI	5.25	5.44
R ₁ = R ₂ = 6, 8-dibromo.						
9	Morpholino	180°	50	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₃ NBr ₂ Cl	2.95	3.17
10	Piperidino	238°	45	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ O ₃ NBr ₂ Cl	2.98	3.18
11	Dimethylamino	220°	40	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ NBr ₂ Cl	3.40	3.60

Thiochroman Oxime.—Thiochromanone (16.4 g.) was refluxed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (7.7g.) and NaHCO₃ (9.3 g.) in 50% EtOH(60 ml) for 2 hr. and the oxime formed was isolated in the usual way; m.p. 95°, yield 17.0 g. (Found : N, 7.46. C₉H₉ONS requires N, 7.82%).

6-Ethoxythiochroman Oxime.—A mixture of 6-ethoxythiochromanone (20.9 g.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (7.7 g.), and NaHCO₃ (9.3 g.), when heated similarly, furnished the oxime in 95% yield (21.0 g.), m.p. 106°. (Found N, 6.02%; C₁₁H₁₃O₂NS requires N, 6.28%).

4-Aminothiochroman Hydrochloride (VI).—Thiochroman oxime (8.5 g.) was reduced by gradual addition of sodium pieces (6.0 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (100 ml) during 30 min. The solvent was removed and water (100 ml) was added and then extracted with ether (3×80 ml). The combined ether extract was washed with water till free of alkali, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and then dry HCl gas was passed into this extract, when 4-aminothiochroman hydrochloride separated. It was filtered, washed with dry ether, and dried; m.p. 208°, yield 7.1 g. (Found: N, 6.72. C₉H₁₂NCIS requires N, 6.9%).

4-Amino-(6-ethoxy)thiochroman hydrochloride (VI) was obtained in the same way from 6-ethoxythiochroman oxime (11.2 g.), sodium (6.0 g.), and anhydrous ethanol (100 ml); m.p. 145°, yield 8.2 g. (Found: N, 5.85. C₁₁H₁₆NCIS requires N, 6.1%).

Schiff bases (VII) of 4-aminothiochroman hydrochloride and 4-amino-(6-ethoxy)-thiochroman hydrochloride were prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of chroman amine hydrochlorides and aromatic aldehydes in anhydrous ethanol for 2 to 4 hr. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue recrystallised from anhydrous ethanol. The m.p.s., yields, and analyses of the Schiff bases are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Aminothiochroman hydrochloride.	Aromatic aldehyde.	Schiff base M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
4-Amino-	<i>p</i> -OMe	180°	90 %	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ONS	4.60	4.95
"	<i>o</i> -Cl	205°	95	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ NCIS	4.48	4.87
4-Amino-(6-ethoxy)-	<i>p</i> -OMe	235°	90	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ NO ₂ S	4.02	4.23
"	<i>o</i> -Cl	238°	92	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ NOClS	3.90	4.22

4-(*o*- & *p*-Substituted benzyl)aminothiochroman Hydrochloride (VIII).—The Schiff bases (0.01*M*) were dissolved in anhydrous ethanol (100 ml) and then reduced catalytically in presence of palladised charcoal at a pressure of 60 lb./sq. in. After filtering the catalyst and removing the solvent, an oily residue was obtained. This was dissolved in ether and dry HCl gas was passed into it whereupon compound (VIII) separated. This was washed with dry ether and dried. The m.p.s, yields, and analyses are recorded in Table V.

TABLE V

Aminothiochroman hydrochloride.	Substituted R'.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
4-amino-	<i>o</i> -Cl, benzyl	220°	60 %	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ NCI ₂ S	4.01	4.20
"	<i>p</i> -OMe, "	225°	55	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ ONClS	4.15	4.26
4-Amino-(6-ethoxy)	<i>o</i> -Cl, "	225°	55	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ ONCl ₂ S	3.80	3.76
"	<i>p</i> -OMe, "	240°	50	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ O ₂ NCIS	3.45	3.53

The following dialkylaminoethyl chloride hydrochlorides were prepared according to Kermack and Wight⁸.

Dialkylaminoethylchloride hydrochloride (viz., 4-morpholinoethyl and 1-piperidinoethyl chloride hydrochlorides) required for the present work were prepared by the action of thionyl chloride on respective 4-morpholino-ethanol and 1-piperidino-ethanol in dry benzene. These in turn were prepared by refluxing morpholine or piperidine with ethylene chlorohydrin in dry benzene for 10 hr.

4-[(*β*-Dialkylamino)ethyl] aminothiochroman (IX).—A mixture of the appropriate dialkylaminoethyl chloride HCl (0.01*M*), thiochromanamine HCl (0.01*M*), anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.02 *M*), and anhydrous ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 6 to 8 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure from the filtrate and the residue was crystallised from anhydrous ethanol. The m.p.s, yields, and analyses are reported in Table VI.

TABLE VI

Thiochroman amine HCl.	Dialkylaminoethyl chloride HCl.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
4-Amino-	Morpholino-	212°	50 %	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ ON ₂ S	9.68	10.09
"	Piperidino-	210°	45	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ S	9.90	10.15
4-Amino-(6-ethoxy)	Morpholino-	238°	45	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.80	8.69
"	Piperidino-	225°	40	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ ON ₂ S	8.55	8.74

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received February 11, 1956.